

IMPACT OF ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR ON JOB PERFORMANCE OF ACADEMICIANS WORKING IN SELECT ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGES

Dr.K. Prabhakumari¹, Mrs.Ruckmani.A²

*¹ Assistant Professor, ² Ph.D Scholar, Department of Management,
Nift-tea college of Knitwear Fashion, Tirupur.*

ABSTRACT

OCBs are thought to have an important impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of work teams and organizations, therefore contributing to the overall productivity. This study evaluates “Impact of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour on Job Performance of Academicians working in Select Arts and Science Colleges in Coimbatore” is undertaken by the researcher to address the research problem. Simple random sampling is used to collect 162 sample academicians for the study. Correlation and Regression are the tools used for analysis. Out of five OCB sub-constructs (Sportsmanship, Altruism, Conscientiousness, Civic virtue and Courtesy) compared with Job Performance it is clear that two constructs (Altruism and Sportsmanship) in combination had the predictive strength of Job Performance. It is recommended that as a part of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour, emotional stability of the working people shall be enhanced by practicing different mock drills on a one to one basis for the fresh faculties to secure experience. Combining hands will result in synchronization and team building among the academicians shall be developed to make sure that the organizational citizenship behaviour elevates the faculty’s satisfaction in their job enhancing their job performance. OCB will become exceptionally beneficial to an organisation and add value directly to the performance of academicians if spiritedly exercised by the select institutions.

Key Words: Academicians, Institutions, Perception, OCB, Job Performance, etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nearly four decades ago, Katz (1964) pointed out the importance of a class of discretionary and spontaneous behaviours that are beyond explicit role requirements, but that are essential for organizational effectiveness. Smith, Organ and Near (1983), in a report of empirical research on the nature and antecedents of such behaviours, conceptualize these contributions as “organizational citizenship behaviour” (OCB), later defined by Organ as “individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization” (Organ, 1988). These behaviours are rather a matter of personal choice, such that their omission is not generally understood as punishable. OCBs are thought to have an important impact on the effectiveness

and efficiency of work teams and organizations, therefore contributing to the overall productivity of the organization.

Organizational Citizenship Behaviours (OCB) are discretionary behaviours on the part of the worker, which are neither expected nor required, and therefore cannot be formally rewarded or punished for the presence or lack of, by the organization. Schnake (1991) gives three reasons why OCB are not affected by organizational influences: (1) OCB are subtle and therefore hard to objectively rate, which makes for difficult inclusion in appraisals; (2) Some forms of OCB may pull people away from their own work to assist another; and (3) Because OCB cannot be contractually required (if they were required behaviours, they would be contractual behaviours, not OCB), the organization cannot punish working people for not performing them. For this reason, OCB is commonly defined in terms of social exchange (Moorman, 1991).

Job Performance is defined as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period of time. Also, distinguishes between sets of behaviours carried out by different individuals and between sets of behaviours carried out by the same individual at different times. Job performance is the accomplishment of those tasks that comprise a person's job (Porter & Lawler, 1968).

Organizational Citizenship Behaviours (OCBs) are a special type of work behaviour that are defined as individual behaviours that are beneficial to the organization and are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system. These behaviours are rather a matter of personal choice, such that their omission is not generally understood as punishable. OCBs are thought to have an important impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of work teams and organizations, therefore contributing to the overall productivity. The five dimensions imply the personality consists of five relatively independent factors that altogether provide different results of each the individual. This study is conducted to find out the Organisational Citizenship Behaviour on Job Performance of Faculty working in select Arts and Science Colleges in Coimbatore. In this study the researcher conducts to study to analyse how well the OCB among faculties helps the institutions.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As per **Dawid Szostek and Aldona Glińska-Neweś (2018)** the organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBs) are the voluntary behaviours in the organization members, which goes beyond the job descriptions, that aims at assisting the co-employees and/or taking care of their operations of the organization. These hypotheses are confirmed on the reasons for a quantitative study that was performed among the 244 employees of the local government units and at the 280 employees who are in the private sector. The analysis of the data brings contrasting outcomes. Generally the employees among the public sector firms involve in OCB frequently than the other

employees in the private sector. Moreover, their OCBs are more on the people orientation. The OCBs of the organization are frequent among the employees in the private sector.

According to **Prameswari Graceshia Adiarani (2019)**, one among the parameters for achieving the employee work engagement is in the job characteristics (Saks, 2006). The research was performed in order to find out that there is the effect of the job characteristics towards the work engagement. The research was performed from 119 employees of the port service company which is located at Surabaya. The orientation on the outcome in the study was found that five of the dimensions in the job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and the feedback) had a significant and positive relationship towards the work engagement.

As per **Perengki Susanto and Mohamad Irfan Maulana, (2020)**, study wants to determine the impact of the satisfaction of job on the job achievement in the organizational citizenship behaviour, the organizational commitment and on the roles of motivation as the mediator with the connection of job achievement and the satisfaction of job at PT. PLN UIP3B Sumatra. The satisfaction of the job did not contain a significant impact directly towards the job performance. The satisfaction of job had the impact hugely on the indirect set of job achievement having the behaviour and the motivation among the organizational citizenship acting as the mediator.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Working people provide organizations with unique human resource capabilities that can create a competitive advantage, and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) is one type of behaviour that may contribute to that advantage. Organisational Citizenship Behaviour has an impact on outcome based on effectiveness and efficiency that is job satisfaction and job performance. Hence, this study evaluates “Impact of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour on Job Performance of Academicians working in Select Arts and Science Colleges in Coimbatore” is undertaken by the researcher to address the research problem.

4. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study the impact of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour on Job Performance of Academicians working in select Arts and Science Colleges in Coimbatore

5. METHODOLOGY

The study is empirical in nature based on survey method. The researcher has used descriptive research design for the research. The primary data collected with the help of the interview schedule considering the impact of organisational citizenship behaviour on job performance taking the academicians as samples from select institutions. The Secondary data related to the study were obtained from various published and unpublished records, annual

reports, booklets, journals, magazines etc. Simple random sampling is used to collect 162 sample academicians for the study. Correlation and Regression are the tools used for analysis.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Some respondents were hesitant to answer the questions and hence, there is a probability of bias where the respondents might not have been serious in giving their opinion. This drawback is not unique to this study, and it a common denominator to all the studies which involve questionnaire based collection of data.

7. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

OCB on Job Performance (Correlation)

Pearson's method inter correlation is a product momentum method compared to examine between quantum of Organisational Citizenship sub-constructs and Job Performance Score perceived by Academicians. The strength of the units measured from strong level to weak level which means, more than 0.7 is strong level, while 0.3 to 0.7 is moderate level and less than 0.3 considered as weak level.

\Table 1: Factors Influencing Job Performance (Descriptive and Correlation)

Constructs	Mean	Std. Deviation	Correlation (Sig.)
Job Performance	20.98	3.384	1.000
Altruism	16.11	3.995	0.393 (0.000)
Conscientiousness	16.78	2.838	0.042 (0.298)
Sportsmanship	16.13	4.754	0.382 (0.000)
Civic virtue	18.56	3.191	0.249 (0.001)
Courtesy	15.19	2.670	-0.043 (0.293)

Result summarizes correlation between relationship between the sub constructs of Organisational Citizenship behaviour (OCB) and Job Performance (JP) scores perceived by Academicians' shows

Low Moderate Positive significant relationship observed high between

- Altruism and Job Performance ($r=0.393$, Sig.0.000)
- Sportsmanship and Job Performance ($r=0.382$, Sig.0.000)

Low positive significant relationship observed between

- Civic Virtue and Job Performance ($r=0.433$, Sig.0.004)

No relationship observed between

- Conscientiousness and Job Performance ($r=0.042$, Sig.0.298)
- Courtesy and Job Performance ($r=-0.043$, Sig.0.293)

INFLUENCE OF ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR ON JOB PERFORMANCE

Regression Analysis

Further, The sub-constructs (Altruism, Conscientiousness, Sportsmanship, Civic virtue and Courtesy) of the Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) Independent Predictor variables examined using enter method by applying Multiple Regression compared with and Job Performance (Dependent) Scores perceived by Academicians. Regression helps to determine the relationship and power of OCB on Job Performance. Therefore, the equation is

$$= 15.258 + 0.259 (X_1: \text{Altruism}) - 0.112 (X_2: \text{Conscientiousness}) + 0.191 (X_3: \text{Sportsmanship}) + 0.105 (X_4: \text{Civic Virtue}) - 0.105 (X_5: \text{Courtesy})$$

Equation reveals all OCB sub-constructs are found to be positive suggesting that Academicians display positive behaviour, individual and group coordination with constructive qualities leading towards their Job Performance. Therefore, the hypothesis framed is

H₁: Significant positive relationship expected between Predictors (OCB sub-constructs) and Job Performance (JP) Scores among Academicians

Multi-collinearity Test

When taking multi-collinearity issues into consideration the predictors based on OCB constructs (Altruism = 1.285, Conscientiousness = 1.180, Sportsmanship = 1.274, Civic Virtue = 1.270 and Courtesy = 1.156) when compared with the Job Satisfaction among Academicians achieved normal distribution thus no multi-collinearity issues identified. As all results in the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) factors not found to have violated the threshold (VIF>5) stated by Ghozali 2006). Further distribution plot (P-P) is exhibited Fig.) Which is self explanatory? Further, the correlation(r) recognizing strength of relationship followed by R^2 (variance explained by OCB sub-constructs i.e. predictor variables), beta-coefficients with critical values presented hereunder:

Table 2: Influence of OCB Factors on Job Performance (Enter Method)

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	B (Unstd. Coeff.)	S.E.	t-value (Sig.)	Collinearity Statistics	
					Tolerance	VIF
Job Satisfaction	Altruism	.259	.067	3.864 (.000)	.778	1.285
	Conscientiousness	-.112	.090	-1.237 (0.218)	.847	1.180
	Sportsmanship	.191	.056	3.404 (0.001)	.785	1.274
	Civic virtue	.105	.083	1.261 (0.209)	.787	1.270
	Courtesy	-.105	.095	-1.104 (0.271)	.865	1.156

Model: R=0.497, R²=0.247, Adj.R²= 0.222, SE=2.984

Fitness: F (5,155) =20.647, P<0.000

Figure 1: Plot measuring OCB on JP (P-P)

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

The overall model (OCB is IV and JS is DV) shows $r=0.497$ shows strong positive relationship while the variance explained by the predictors shows $R^2=0.247$, Adj. $R^2=0.222$) which is reasonably good enough in predicting the OCB factors on Job Performance perceived by Academicians. Further, the fitness of the model using ANOVA $F(5,155)=10.152$, Sig.0.000 declares achievement of statistical significance.

Table predicting the achievement of statistical relationship of OCB constructs (IV) when compared with Job Performance scores (DV) perceived by Academicians shows the first construct is Altruism based OCB achieved positive relationship with Job Performance $\beta=0.259$, $SE=0.067$, $t=3.864$, Sig.0.000 is statistically proved to reject H_0 . Second construct is Conscientiousness based OCB achieved negative relationship with Job Performance $\beta=-0.112$, $SE=0.090$, $t=-1.237$, Sig.0.218 however, did not achieved statistical significance thus, accepting H_0 . Third construct is Sportsmanship based OCB achieved positive relationship with Job Performance $\beta=0.191$, $SE=0.056$, $t=3.404$, Sig.0.001 is statistically proved to reject H_0 . Fourth construct is Civic Virtue based OCB achieved positive relationship with Job Performance $\beta=0.105$, $SE=0.083$, $t=1.261$, Sig.0.209 however, did not achieved statistical significance therefore, accepting H_0 . Fifth construct is Courtesy based OCB did not achieved relationship (@ 5% level) with Job Performance $\beta=-0.105$, $SE=0.095$, $t=-1.104$, Sig.0.271 also statistically did not prove significant to accept H_0 . Further, stepwise method adopted to evaluate the contribution of each independent (OCB) construct measuring Job satisfaction perceived by Academicians is presented hereunder:

Table 3: Factors Influencing Job Performance (Stepwise method)

Models	OCB Constructs (IV)	B (Unstd. Coeff.)	S.E.	t-value (Sig.)	R ² & F (df), P-Value
Model-1	Altruism	.333	.062	5.392 (0.000)	R²=0.155 F(1,159)=29.075, Sig.0.000
Model-2	Altruism	.254	.063	4.047 (0.000)	R²=0.226 F(2,158)=23.109, P=0.000
	Sportsmanship	.202	.053	3.827 (0.000)	

Dependent Variable: Job Performance

Altruism (Model-1) based Organisational Citizenship Behaviour contributed 16% (approx.) change in Job Performance. While, adding Altruism with Sportsmanship (Model-2) the change in Job Performance observed to be 7% (approx.) contribution of these two factors. Though, two factors contributed significantly, Altruism contributed highly towards influencing the Job Performance perceived highly among Academicians in the select institutions considered for the study.

8. SUMMARY OF RESULTS

- Stepwise regression selected to observe the ultimate grouping of predictor variables (OCB constructs) which explains the maximum variance in the outcome (Job Performance) considering R-square. Out of five OCB sub-constructs (Sportsmanship, Altruism, Conscientiousness, Civic virtue and Courtesy) compared with Job Performance it is clear that two constructs (Altruism and Sportsmanship) in combination had the predictive strength of Job Performance. The first OCB sub-construct represented by Altruism recorded Low moderate ($R^2=0.155$) at 15.5% level of variance in predicting Job Performance followed by Altruism & Sportsmanship ($R^2=0.226$) predicted 22.6% in which R square change observed with Altruism contributed 7.1% variance in predicting job performance. Thus the independent variables (Altruism and Sportsmanship or OCB sub-constructs) progressively identified that also provides an additional diminishing contribution of R^2 value when predicting the job performance among Academicians.

9. SUGGESTIONS

- It is recommended that as a part of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour, emotional stability of the working people shall be enhanced by practicing different mock drills on a one to one basis for the fresh faculties to secure experience. Also, giving psychological counselling to the experienced can calm their emotions and espouse themselves during tricky situations / difficult tasks. In this regard, mock sessions / counsel can be conducted intermittently covering personality, technical and behavioural facets may definitely support the academicians towards self realization without compromising their emotional stability which can certainly support them to concentrate and improve their weak areas that can significantly improve their satisfaction and job performance.
- It is recommended that an accurate agenda shall be organized and the essential management approach shall be conveyed to every individual in the organisation. This avoids responsibility going into a particular shoulder which may be a burden to individuals. Combining hands will result in synchronization and team building among the academicians shall be developed to make sure that the organizational citizenship behaviour elevates the faculty's satisfaction in their job enhancing their job performance.

10. CONCLUSION

- Behaviour of working individuals are unrestricted that needs to be directly or explicitly recognized by promoting proper reward system that may have collective impact on the organisations. Therefore, OCB will become exceptionally beneficial to an organisation and add value directly to the performance of academicians if spiritedly exercised by the select institutions.

11. REFERENCES

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